

References

Fitzpatrick, E. L. 1985, ApJ, 299, 219

Appendix E: Omitted objects

Sk-69° 83 For this star, we find a sign of binarity in He II $\lambda 4686$, where it is blue shifted relative to all the other lines, indicating the existence of an emission from a primary hotter object combined with the emission of a cooler object. We also find signs of two components in He II $\lambda 5411$ and H γ

Sk-67° 197, Sk-66° 152, Sk-67° 168, Sk-70° 50 These objects were omitted from the analysis due to H α and He II $\lambda 4686$ having two symmetrical emission peaks with a narrow absorption feature in the line center which is indicative of a non-spherically symmetric geometry such as a circumstellar disk.

Sk-66° 50 The spectrum of this object showed clear binary signatures in the form of double peaked absorption in H β , He and H γ in addition to the odd morphology of H α .

Appendix F: Appendix F: Comments on individual stars

Sk-66° 171, Fig. H.1, Fig. I.1 When considering helium lines other than He I $\lambda 4471$ He II $\lambda 4542$, one might prefer a model with a slightly higher temperature. The other glaring issue is with the H α , although the morphology of the model line is similar to the observation, we do find that the centre of the emission in the observation is slightly red shifted relative to all other lines. In the UV and FUV the model fits the observations very well. Fig. I.1 shows the fit for the entire spectrum, where for this object include a fit for the absorption profiles for Ly α through Ly η , which were calculated using H I column density $\log N(HI) = 20.7 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (Fitzpatrick 1985). The observed He II $\lambda 4686$ emission is predicted in absorption.

Sk-68° 155, Fig. H.2, Fig. I.2 This star with $v \sin i = 80 \text{ km/s}$ is the fastest rotator in our sample, which is reflected in the relatively broad metal and helium lines. The small dip in the centre of the emission in H α could be an indication of an optically thick disk forming around the star, other than that the overall quality of the fit is very good. The model overpredicts the He II $\lambda 4686$ absorption.

Sk-69° 279, Fig. H.3, Fig. I.3 This is one of two hypergiants in our sample, which is classified as such by the extremely strong emission in H α and the P Cygni shape in higher Balmer lines and in He I $\lambda 4471$, therefore, we use H η for estimating $\log g$, as all other Balmer lines are contaminated by winds and take He I $\lambda 4026$ and He II $\lambda 5411$ as primary diagnostics to obtain the temperature. The overall fit is quite good considering all the challenges that come with fitting the spectra of emission line objects, with the exception of He II $\lambda 4686$ line, where the predicted emission is weaker than the observed.

Sk-71° 41, Fig. H.4, Fig. I.4 For this object, we were not able to reproduce the observed unsaturated silicon lines Si IV $\lambda \lambda 1393 - 1403$ even with models with extremely clumped winds $f_{\text{vol}} = 0.03 - 0.02$. We note two other peculiarities, first of which is the large discrepancy between v_{∞} obtained from the C IV $\lambda \lambda 1548 - 1551$ ($\approx 1500 \text{ km s}^{-1}$) and Si IV $\lambda \lambda 1394 - 1403$

($\approx 1300 \text{ km s}^{-1}$). The other peculiarity is the unexplainably broad O III $\lambda 5592$ line.

Sk-68° 135, Fig. H.5, Fig. I.5 This is second hypergiant in our sample. Just as for Sk-69° 279, we estimate $\log g$ from H η . But unlike the other hypergiant, we obtain a more reliable value for T_{eff} because the helium lines do are less contaminated by the extreme winds. We obtain decent fits for most lines, with the exception of the strong He II $\lambda 4686$ emission, which is predicted in absorption in the model.

Sk-67° 5, Fig. H.6, Fig. I.6 For this object, we were not able to replicate the morphology of H α . The most glaring issue in this fit is the helium abundance, and therefore the hydrogen abundance as well.

Sk-68° 52, Fig. H.7, Fig. I.7 This is one of the early B0 supergiants that shows weak He II lines. We chose not to fit He II lines, as increasing the temperature of the model by a mere 500 K does indeed give a better fit for He II lines but drastically weakens S III lines. Overall, we obtain an excellent fit for most lines.

Sk-69° 43, Fig. H.8, Fig. I.8 In the case of this object, as for Sk-67° 2, we were able to accurately reproduce the emission in H α but not the broad, blueshifted absorption.

Sk-68° 140, Fig. H.9, Fig. I.9 The unsaturated Si IV $\lambda \lambda 1393 - 1403$ lines, which suggests clumpier winds, were not reproduced by our models even with much smaller volume filling factors. The fit for this stars serves as a good example of the consequences of excluding X-rays from our models, as seen on Fig. I.9, the strong P Cygni C IV $\lambda 1550$ in the observations is much weaker in the model, this is because in this temperature range C III dominates the ionization structure, but due to X-rays generated by shocks, we observe the enhanced C IV line.

Sk-67° 2, Fig. H.10, Fig. I.10 The overall fit for this object is very good. In this case, we obtain a good fit for H α emission, but we were unable to fit the blueshifted absorption.

Sk-67° 14, Fig. H.11, Fig. I.11 We notice on this object that Si IV $\lambda \lambda 1393 - 1403$ would suggest less emissive winds (higher volume f_{vol}), whereas Al III $\lambda \lambda 1856 - 1860$ would suggest more emissive winds (lower volume f_{vol}).

Sk-69° 52, Fig. H.12, Fig. I.12 For this star, we were not able to reproduce the odd morphology of H α , which seem to have a sudden cut-off and the peak of the emission.

Sk-67° 78, Fig. H.13, Fig. I.13 The most noticeable issue with the fit of this object is the extended wings and the blue shifted absorption of the model H α , which we could not eliminate. Although, we were able to obtain a good match to the emission in H α .

Sk-70° 16, Fig. H.14, Fig. I.14 For this object we obtain a very good fit, except for H α , where we could not reproduce the weak, but broad absorption.

Sk $-68^\circ 8$, Fig. H.15, Fig. I.15 For this object, we were able to obtain a good fit for $H\alpha$ emission and to the general morphology. We do note the infilling of the $H\gamma$ line core, which could be due to nebular contamination. The $\text{Si II } \lambda\lambda 6347 - 6371$ lines in the model match the observations quite well. This can be used as a sanity check for determining the effective temperature for mid and late B-supergiants.

Sk $-67^\circ 195$, Fig. H.16, Fig. I.16 For this low luminosity late B-supergiant we do not find any viable oxygen lines, therefore we do not change the oxygen mass fraction when applying our pipeline to this star. We consider the mass-loss rate of this object to be an upper limit due to $H\alpha$ being fully in absorption. We note that the predicted $\text{Si II } \lambda\lambda 6347 - 6371$ lines excellently match the observed, albeit we did not use them as diagnostics.

Appendix G: Spectral energy distribution (SED)

In Fig. [G.1](#) we present the SED fits for the entire sample.

Fig. G.1: Spectral energy distribution for all the stars in our sample. Red solid line: model SED, Black solid line: observed SED. The photometric points are indicated as blue circles.

Fig. G.1: continued

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Appendix H: Line fitting for individual stars

Fig. **H.1-H.16** are the individual diagnostic line fits for each star in our sample. On each row, from top to bottom, are the diagnostic lines used to determine the effective temperature, the effective surface gravity, the wind density parameters (mass-loss rate, β , clumping parameters), the helium abundance, the nitrogen abundance, the carbon abundance, and the oxygen abundance, respectively.

Fig. H.1: Individual line fits for Sk -66° 171. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 410 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.2: Individual line fits for Sk -68° 155. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 240 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.3: Individual line fits for Sk -69° 279. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 230 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.4: Individual line fits for Sk-71° 41. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 260 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.5: Individual line fits for Sk -68° 135. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 270 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.6: Individual line fits for Sk $-67^\circ 5$. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 295 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.7: Individual line fits for Sk -68° 52. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 255 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.9: Individual line fits for Sk -68° 140. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 260 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.10: Individual line fits for Sk -67° 2. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 320 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.11: Individual line fits for Sk -67° 14. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 300 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.12: Individual line fits for Sk -69° 52. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 260 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.13: Individual line fits for Sk -67° 78. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 310 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.14: Individual line fits for Sk -70° 16. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 265 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.15: Individual line fits for Sk -68° 8. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 250 \text{ km s}^{-1}$

Fig. H.16: Individual line fits for Sk -67° 195. Black solid line: observed spectrum. Red solid line: spectrum of the best fitting model. The observed spectrum is corrected for $v_{\text{rad}} = 300\text{km s}^{-1}$

Appendix I: Overall fitting for individual stars

Fig. I.1-I.16 are the fits for the overall spectrum of each star in our sample.

Fig. I.1: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -66° 171. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. Second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, respectively, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features. For this star, we fit the absorption profiles for $Ly\alpha$ through $Ly\eta$, which were calculated using H I column density $\log N(HI) = 20.7$ cm $^{-2}$ (Fitzpatrick 1985).

Fig. I.2: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -68° 155. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. The second and third panels are the COS G130M+G160M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, respectively, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.3: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -69° 279. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. Second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.4: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -71° 41. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. Second panel is STIS E140M FUV, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.5: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -68° 135. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. Second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.6: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk $-67^{\circ} 5$. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ $\lambda 950$, $Ly\gamma$ $\lambda 973$, and $Ly\beta$ $\lambda 1026$. Second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, respectively, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ $\lambda 1216$, O I + P II $\lambda 1302$, C II $\lambda 1335$, Si II $\lambda 1527$, and Al II $\lambda 1671$. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.7: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -68° 52. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. Second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, respectively, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.8: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -69° 43. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. Second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, respectively, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.9: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -68° 140. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. Second and third panels are COS G130M+G160M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, respectively, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.10: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -67° 2. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. Second and third panels are STIS E140M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, respectively, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.11: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -67° 14. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as Ly δ λ 950, Ly γ λ 973, and Ly β λ 1026. Second and third panels are COS G130M+G160M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, and we note some interstellar features: Ly α λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.12: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk $-69^{\circ} 52$. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ $\lambda 950$, $Ly\gamma$ $\lambda 973$, and $Ly\beta$ $\lambda 1026$. Second and third panels are COS G130M+G160M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ $\lambda 1216$, O I + P II $\lambda 1302$, C II $\lambda 1335$, Si II $\lambda 1527$, and Al II $\lambda 1671$. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.13: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -67° 78. From the top, the first panel is the FUV FUSE range, containing interstellar features such as $Ly\delta$ λ 950, $Ly\gamma$ λ 973, and $Ly\beta$ λ 1026. Second and third panels are COS G130M+G160M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, respectively, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.14: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -70° 16. From the top, the first and second panels are COS G130M+G160M FUV and COS G160M+G185M NUV spectral ranges, respectively, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.15: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -68° 8. From the top, the first and second panels are COS G130M+G160M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, respectively, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.

Fig. I.16: An overall view of the best fit (red solid line) to key regions of the observed spectrum (black solid line) of Sk -67° 195. From the top, the first and second panels are COS G130M+G160M FUV and STIS E230M NUV spectral ranges, respectively, and we note some interstellar features: $Ly\alpha$ λ 1216, O I + P II λ 1302, C II λ 1335, Si II λ 1527, and Al II λ 1671. The rest of the panels are the UVB and VIS XShooter spectra, with the break between the two arms at ≈ 5600 Å. The lines Ca II H + K and Na I D are interstellar features.